

Peculiarities of the use of the Mathematics software complex for the numerical solution of the given equation

Using the "Mathematics" software package, we will obtain a numerical solution to the equation with a "turning point" for given functions $F(x)$ and initial conditions.

$$\varepsilon^2 \frac{d^2 y(x)}{dx^2} + F(x)y(x) = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$\varepsilon^2 \frac{d^2 y(x)}{dx^2} + x^3 y(x) = 0, \quad (14)$$

where $\varepsilon^2 \ll 1$

Plot [x^3 , { x , -1, 1}, Axes Label → { x , F }]

Fig. 1. Graph of the function $F(x) = x^3$

Program for numerical solution of a differential equation in the "Mathematics" system.

```
NDSolve[{0.01*y''[x]+(x^3)*y[x]==0,y[0]==0,y'[1]==1},y,{x,0,1}]
```

```
{{y->InterpolatingFunction[{{0.,1.}},<>]}}
```

```
N1=Plot[Evaluate[y[x]/.%,{x,-1,1},AxesLabel->{x,y}]
```

InterpolatingFunction: dmval : Input value {-0.999959} lies outside the range of data in the interpolating function. Extrapolation will be used.

Fig. 2. Overlaid graph of solutions in the interval $(x, 0, +1)$

```
NDSolve[{0.01*y''[x]+(x^3)*y[x]==0,y[0]==0,y'[1]==1},y,{x,-1,0}]
```

```
{y->InterpolatingFunction[{{-1.,0.}},<>]}
```

```
N2=Plot[Evaluate[y[x]/.%],{x,-1,1},AxesLabel->{x,y}]
```


Fig. 3. Overlaid graph of solutions in the interval $(x, -1, 0)$

```
Show[N1,N2]
```


Fig. 4. Overlaid graph of the solution in the interval $(x, -1, +1)$

Solution of the equation for a continuous interval of a variable $(x, -1, +1)$

```
NDSolve[{0.01*y''[x]+(x^3)*y[x]==0,y[0]==0,y'[1]==1},y,
{x,-1,1}]
```

```
{y->InterpolatingFunction[{{-1.,1.}},<>]}
```

```
N3=Plot[Evaluate[y[x]/.%,{x,-1,1},AxesLabel->{x,F(x)}]
```


Fig. 5. Solution graph in the interval $(x, -1, +1)$

```
Show[N1,N2,N3]
```


Fig. 6. Overlaid graph of solutions in intervals $(x, -1, 0)$ та $(x, 0, +1)$

Fractional degree of a function $F(x)$.

$$\varepsilon^2 \frac{d^2 y(x)}{dx^2} + x^{1.5} y(x) = 0 \quad (15)$$

Plot $[x^{1.5}, \{x, -1, 1\}]$, Axes Label $\rightarrow \{x, F(x)\}$

Fig. 7. Function graph $F(x) = x^{1.5}$

```
NDSolve[{0.01*y''[x]+x^1.5*y[x]==0,y[0]==0,y'[1]==1},y,{x,-1,1}]
```

```
{y->InterpolatingFunction[{{-1.,1.}},<>]}
```

```
N1=Plot[Evaluate[y[x]/.%,{x,-1,1},AxesLabel->{x,y}]
```


Fig. 8. Numerical solution of the equation in the interval $(-1, +1)$

The "Mathematics" system does not allow you to construct a function with a "turning point" due to the appearance of a complex value of the function and, accordingly, obtain a numerical solution of equation (13) on the full given interval of the variable.

In this case, only the asymptotic approach provides an opportunity to obtain a reliable solution, which consists of three components: on one side of the interval of the variable from the "turning point", on the other side and in the vicinity of the "turning point".